

Experimental Validation of XPM Mitigation Using a Generalizable Multi-Task Learning Neural Network

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We address the development of efficient neural networks (NN)-based post-equalizers in long-haul coherent-detection dense wavelength-division multiplexing optical transmission systems. To achieve a high level of generalization of the NN-based equalizers, we propose to employ multi-task learning (MTL). MTL refers to a single shared machine learning (NN) model that can perform multiple different (albeit related) tasks. We verify the good performance of the developed MTL equalizer model using experimental data as compared to the previously proposed approaches. Furthermore, we report how MTL can improve performance compared to single-task counterparts. We also demonstrate that reducing the complexity of the resulting MTL equalizer is possible without essential performance compromise.

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Mitigation or control of the impact of the Kerr nonlinearity is important in various scientific and practical problems ranging from optical communications to supercontinuum generation. Artificial neural networks (NNs) are already actively used for modeling, analysis, and, where appropriate, compensation of nonlinear effects (see e.g. [1] and references therein). To the best of our knowledge, for the first time, we propose to enhance the flexibility and generalizability of NN-based optical fiber channel equalizers in coherent-detection dense wavelength-division multiplexing (DWDM) systems by using multi-task learning (MTL) – the concept widely used in different areas for the development of efficient machine learning models[2, 3]. The main idea of the MTL concept is to improve the performance of multiple related learning tasks by sharing and leveraging useful information. In our work here, we specifically address how the MTL works with the equalizers mitigating self-phase modulation (SPM) and cross-phase modulation (XPM). SPM and XPM cause significant signal distortions, degrading performance in DWDM optical

communication networks. Among the numerous benefits of the NN equalization, we note that the NN-based solutions[4, 5] can offer lower computational complexity than traditional mitigation techniques, such as digital back-propagation (DBP)[6]. By leveraging the MTL, the proposed NN-based equalizer can dynamically learn and compensate for these nonlinear distortions without retraining the NN, adapting to different channel spacings and varying levels of XPM. The NN equalizer architecture that we use in our study incorporates convolutional and bidirectional long short-term memory (biLSTM) layers, the composite NN architecture that demonstrated the best performance in similar nonlinearity mitigation tasks[7, 8].

DWDM with coherent detection is one of the core modern optical communication technologies, enabling high-capacity data transmission over long distances[9]. However, the performance of DWDM systems is fundamentally limited by nonlinear effects arising from the Kerr nonlinearity in optical fibers. Traditional nonlinearity mitigation solutions can partially compensate for XPM distortions by treating XPM as a time-varying intersymbol interference process for the zeroth order XPM contribution (phase and polarization-rotation noise)[4, 10]. However, compensation of the higher-order XPM contributions in the multi-channel/carrier systems requires relatively complex solutions, e.g. Volterra equalizers[11, 12] or multi-channel full-field DBP[13]. NN-based equalizers are a promising alternative to mitigate nonlinear distortions in multi-channel systems with relatively good performance at moderate complexity[4, 14].

In this work, we examine how the NN-based equalizers address varying levels of XPM, using the experimental datasets where we alter the number of neighboring channels and the spacing between the channel under test (CUT) and its neighbors. We transition from a system limited by intra-channel impairment, SPM alone (with 1 THz spacing between CUT and its neighbors) to a system constrained by both SPM and XPM (with 50 GHz channel spacing), see Fig. 1a. In particular, the integration of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and biLSTM networks has shown great potential in capturing the intricate patterns of SPM and XPM. Unlike Ref. [4], we focus on feeding the NN with the information solely from the CUT and applying MTL[2, 15] to enhance the model's generalizability with the benefits of improving the overall performance. The flexibility

Fig. 1. (a) NN Equalizer architecture with 1D-CNN and biLSTM layers, taking DWDM data of CUT with different channel spacing as an input; (b) MTL: only one model is required for various situations with different channel spacing.

of the NN is crucial, as, in the real world, channel spacing can vary significantly based on resource availability, requirements, and unexpected changes in the channel allocation. To compare performance and adaptability, MTL is benchmarked against the traditional single-task learning (STL) method. The MTL does not require re-training to cope with the variation of channel spacing at deployment, which can be useful in practical applications. With STL training, multiple models with different sets of weights are required to provide acceptable performance, while *only one model is needed when the equalizer is trained with MTL*.

For the first time, we present a ‘single’ NN-based equalizer that mitigates varying levels of XPM using MTL, based on experimental data, without the need for re-training to achieve strong performance. The MTL model’s generalizability without re-training is critical for real-world transmission where channel spacing is not necessarily constant. We show the NN’s potential to mitigate XPM without additional information about neighboring channels (only information from the signals leaked from the adjacent channels). The potential for reducing the computational complexity of our model is also explored and assessed at the end of our study.

Learning XPM via the Multi-Task Learning. In this work, we trained the NN on different datasets with various channel spacing (different degrees of XPM). The channel spacing for each dataset is 1000, 500, 400, 300, 200, 100, and 50 GHz from CUT, see Fig. 1a. In this way, we can observe how the NN tackles varying levels of XPM, focusing on the nonlinear regime. We use MTL to train the NN to attain generalizability. The MTL, illustrated in Fig. 1b, enables a single NN to perform in different channel spacing scenarios, as it does not require re-training for different band spacing. In the MTL, the NN is trained jointly with multiple datasets from multiple related tasks; the tasks refer to different channel spacing. MTL leverages shared representations to enhance the generalizability of the NN across the different intensities of XPM. With the MTL, the model learns the different datasets with random channel spacing at each training epoch, allowing the model to gain broader knowledge. MTL also reduces hardware costs as the shared weights are fixed, resulting in the simplification of the multipliers[16]. In the case that the different tasks are sufficiently related, the shared representation in MTL helps improve generalization, even for tasks that might not perform as well in their STL[3]. We conducted a comparative analysis to assess the MTL’s performance against the traditional STL model. STL is a common training approach where the NN learns to provide the output for a “specific” task. STL enables the

NN to excel at a specific task but often underperforms in other tasks. Ultimately, multiple models are required at the inference phase to guarantee the best performance.

The NN architecture described in Fig. 1a, includes a 1D-CNN layer with 117 filters, a kernel size of 3 and LeakyReLU¹ activation, followed by a biLSTM layer with 98 units, and another 1D-CNN layer with 2 filters to recover real and imaginary parts of X-polarization output. The NN structure with 1D-CNN and biLSTM has proven superior in nonlinear compensation compared to other NN types[8, 17, 18]. The NN received 221 input symbols to simultaneously recover 189 output symbols. The training dataset contained 2¹⁹ independent symbols and, at every epoch, 2¹⁸ symbols were randomly picked for training. For the testing and validation, a never-before-seen dataset with 2¹⁷ symbols was utilized. The datasets were created using a pseudo-random binary sequence (PRBS) of order 32. The training was carried out with a mini-batch size of 3786, a learning rate of 9.0816×10^{-4} , mean square error loss, and the Adam algorithm. Adam is an optimization algorithm that extends Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) by using adaptive learning rates and momentum to improve convergence speed and stability. We also adopted early stopping and data augmentation, adding slight

¹Unlike ReLU, LeakyReLU allows a small gradient for negative values to ensure that the neurons continue learning and helps with the weight updates.

Fig. 2. Schematics of the experimental setup used in our work, where the input of the NN is the soft output (before decision unit) of the DSP Rx (see more details in the paper body).

Fig. 3. (a) The Q-factor versus the launch power for the NN trained with MTL and STL, compared to the CDC and DBP 3 STpS; (b) Q-factor gain for MTL models with respect to the CDC performance; (c) Q-factor at 1 dBm launch power of MTL compared to the CDC and two models trained solely with datasets of 50 GHz and 1000 GHz, respectively.

random noise to the training data to avoid overfitting. The optimal hyper-parameters were found by the Bayesian optimizer (BO), given the range of acceptable complexity. The BO was applied specifically to optimize the hyperparameters for the STL model trained on the 50 GHz channel spacing, due to its most exposure to nonlinear impairments like XPM. Once the optimal hyperparameters were found for the STL model, we applied the same set of hyperparameters for training the MTL model. The model received four input features derived from the in-phase and quadrature components of the complex signal (X_I , X_Q , Y_I , and Y_Q) from X and Y polarizations, respectively. This proposed NN only considers the data from the CUT without exploring the information from adjacent channels. The models with MTL were trained for 1500 epochs (can compensate for all channel spacings considered), whereas the traditional training models were trained for 1000 epochs (to compensate for one channel spacing). To reduce the training complexity of STL training, transfer learning (TL) was applied[19]. TL adapts the knowledge acquired in one task to the different tasks (different channel spacing). We transferred the knowledge from 50 GHz to the larger channel spacing as the model learns and adapts better from a more severe XPM situation. Even though TL reduces the training complexity, it does not contribute to the inference/implementation complexity, as the multiple sets of weights of the NNs are still required for different transmission scenarios.

Experimental setup. Fig. 2 depicts the experimental setup, as in Ref. [8], where the 16-QAM dual-polarization (DP) 34.4 Gbd symbol sequence was mapped from the data bits generated by a $2^{32} - 1$ order pseudorandom binary sequence at the transmitter. Then, the channel bandwidth was limited to 37.5 GHz by the root-raised-cosine (RRC) filter with 0.1 roll-off. The processed digital samples were passed to a digital-to-analog converter (DAC) operating at 88 Gsamples/s. The DAC outputs were amplified using a four-channel electrical amplifier, which drove a DP in-phase/quadrature Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM), which in turn modulated a continuous waveform carrier generated by an external cavity laser operating at $\lambda = 1.55 \mu\text{m}$. The resulting optical signal was transmitted over $9 \times 50 \text{ km}$ TrueWave Classic (TWC) fiber spans with EDFA, with up to 95 neighboring channels (100G QPSK, 50 GHz ITU grid). We consider the WDM channels with different channel spacing, see Fig. 1a. TWC fiber parameters were: attenuation coefficient $\alpha = 0.23 \text{ dB/km}$, dispersion coefficient $D = 2.8 \text{ ps/(nm} \cdot \text{km)}$ and nonlinear coefficient $\gamma = 2.5 (\text{W} \cdot \text{km})^{-1}$.

At Rx, an integrated coherent receiver converted the signal to the electrical domain, which was sampled at 50 Gsamples/s using a digital sampling oscilloscope. The signal underwent offline DSP processing as in Ref. [20], including chromatic dispersion compensation (CDC), MIMO equalization, carrier frequency offset correction, clock recovery, and a pilot-aided carrier recovery². The resulting symbols were fed as an NN input for nonlinear mitigation. Finally, at the output of the NN, the pre-forward error correction (pre-FEC) Q-factor was evaluated.

Results and Discussion. Fig. 3a presents the Q-factor as a function of launch power for different channel spacing. The Q-factor was calculated by: $Q = 20 \log_{10} \left[\sqrt{2} \text{erfc}^{-1}(2\text{BER}) \right]$. Albeit the MTL was not optimized for the specific cases like in the STL, the MTL models still slightly outperformed the traditional STL approach, especially when the launch power was higher, or the regime was extremely nonlinear. This advantage of MTL was also reported in [3]. We attribute this to the MTL's ability to acquire knowledge across all XPM levels simultaneously. This result shows that the MTL models partially learn the complex patterns associated with the XPM, enhancing the Q-factor compared to the CDC. The DBP with 3 steps per span (STpS) did not perform well, providing only a small gain because the DBP only compensated for SPM; TWC's high nonlinearity coefficient made XPM more significant[21]. The NNs also show the potential to mitigate real-world component-induced impairments beyond Kerr nonlinear effects. The component-induced corruptions can be the effects of the transceivers (ADC/DAC, drive amplifier, or MZM), also observed in [22].

Fig. 3b depicts the Q-factor improvement achieved by MTL compared to the CDC for different channel spacings. Considering the optimum power when the channel spacings were 50 GHz and 1000 GHz, the gain of the 50 GHz scenario was around 0.2 dB higher than in the case of 1000 GHz spacing. To assess

²The carrier recovery block in Fig. 2 includes both frequency offset compensation and carrier phase recovery

	CDC	DBP 3 STpS	Original MTL	MTL with 8 WC
Q-factor [dB]	7.81	8.08	9.7	8.9
RMpS	109	2928	209884	5930

Table 1. Q-factor and computational complexity of different methods.

the performance and robustness of the MTL, we consider the launch power where the fiber nonlinearity started to play a noticeable role, i.e., exceeding -3 dBm. For a narrower channel spacing (SPM and XPM are essential), the gain was even more pronounced than that for a wider channel spacing (where the XPM impact becomes less pronounced). With the increase in power, the difference between the gain at 50 GHz and 1000 GHz channel spacings also increased: the difference was 0.3 dB at -3 dBm launch power, 0.8 dB at -1 dBm launch power and 1.2 dB at 1 dBm launch power. This observation shows that the NN trained with MTL efficiently compensates both SPM and XPM.

To emphasize the NN's adaptability and efficiency in mitigating XPM, Fig. 3c shows that at the 1 dBm launch power, the MTL model outperforms both traditional STL models trained on 50 GHz and 1000 GHz channel spacings and the CDC. This showcases the MTL's superior generalization capability across different scenarios. While the STL models trained for specific spacings perform well for the cases matching the specific training conditions, they perform worse when applied to other scenarios. Even though the model trained with 50 GHz spacing data had only a slight drop in Q-factor compared to the MTL, this difference may be larger for other launch powers. Notably, the model trained on 50 GHz spacing generalizes better, likely due to greater exposure to XPM dynamics in DWDM systems, unlike the 1000 GHz model that exhibits reduced adaptability due to limited XPM exposure.

Tab. 1 shows the Q-factor and computational complexity in terms of number of real multiplications per equalized symbol (RmpS)[5] for CDC, DBP with 3 STpS, original MTL model, and the reduced complexity MTL model using Weight Clustering (WC) technique, detailed in [23]. The WC model groups similar weights into clusters and shares a single value within each cluster; in our case, we used 8 clusters. The WC model was included to demonstrate the possibility of reducing the computational complexity in the MTL NN-based equalizer. While DBP offers about half the complexity of the MTL model with 8 WC, it only compensates for SPM and not XPM. We can notice the trade-off between the Q-factor and complexity. The numbers reported in Tab. 1 were assessed using the dataset considering the optimum launch power of the 50 GHz channel spacing scenario. Note that the NN in this work was not optimized for lower complexity.

In Ref. [15], the MTL model was used to equalize symbols when the channel characteristics varied, and a trade-off between the Q-factor of individual tasks and the overall performance was observed. In the current study, the MTL model applied for varying XPM levels did not demonstrate the same trade-off. Instead, the MTL framework contributed to enhancing each specific task's performance. The MTL's performance boost and its ability to work without re-training are notable advantages compared to employing several STL models for different channel spacings in traditional training. Additionally, in this study, our NN leveraged the dataset from the same experimental setup and a similar NN architecture as in Ref. [8], but our model here was designed to recover multiple output symbols simultaneously. Multi-symbol output not only reduces the computational complexity per symbol but also reveals a superior performance compared to its single-symbol counterpart.

In conclusion, we employed multi-task learning (MTL) to develop a neural network (NN)-based equalizer capable of mitigating nonlinear impairments in coherent-detection DWDM systems. Learning from the experimental data and leveraging the MTL concept, our MTL NN-based equalizer demonstrates excellent adaptability to varying levels of SPM and XPM.

The proposed MTL model has remarkable generalizability as we need only a "single" model without the necessity of re-training for different channel spacing or diverse levels of XPM. We showed that the MTL model outperforms the CDC, DBP with 3 STpS, and the "traditional" single-task model. In our case, the MTL optimized the performance across all studied tasks without compromising the performance of individual tasks; moreover, we revealed that the MTL can even enhance the performance for specific tasks. Additionally, we explored and assessed the potential for reducing the computational complexity of our MTL-based model, making it more viable for real-world optical communication networks, and demonstrated the possibility of essential complexity reduction for our MTL equalizer without a significant penalty in its performance.

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